

Kinetics of Silver(I)-Catalysed Oxidation of Some Aromatic Azo Compounds by Peroxydisulphate

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The kinetics of oxidation of some aromatic azo compounds by peroxydisulphate catalysed by silver(I), was investigated. The reaction is first order with respect to peroxydisulphate and silver(I) and zero order in each of the azo compounds. The reaction exhibits induction period which decreases with increasing silver(I) concentration. Increase in ionic strength decreases the rate. The reaction mixture initiates vinyl polymerization.

THE kinetics of peroxydisulphate oxidation of a number of organic and inorganic substrates has been reported and reviewed.^{1,2} However, a survey of the literature has shown that the kinetics of oxidation of azo compounds by peroxydisulphate has not been made so far. Hence a detailed kinetic study of the oxidation of some aromatic azo compounds by peroxydisulphate catalysed by silver(I) seemed desirable. A separate investigation has shown that the uncatalysed oxidation is very slow under the experimental conditions employed. The results indicate a radical chain mechanism.

Experimental

All the azo compounds used were twice recrystallised. All the other materials used were of analytical reagent grade. The azo compounds studied are pink in aqueous acid solution. For example, methyl orange and methyl red have pK values 3.4 and 5.0 respectively and hence in acid medium these two would exist in protonated form. The course of the reaction was followed by measuring the optical

density of the unreacted compound in aqueous sulphuric acid medium using a green filter (500-530 nm). The ionic strength was maintained constant with sodium bisulphate. Under these conditions Beer's Law was obeyed by each of the azo compounds and all the other materials concerned have negligible absorption. Under the experimental conditions employed for the catalysed reaction, the rate of uncatalysed reaction was found to be negligibly small in comparison with the rates of the catalysed reaction just at the end of the induction period (Table 1). Hence no correction has been applied for uncatalysed reaction while analysing the rate data.

Stoichiometry: The stoichiometry of the reaction was investigated by the addition of a known excess of the azo compound to peroxydisulphate in 1 N H₂SO₄, 2.4 × 10⁻³ M AgNO₃ and 8% V/V acetic acid solution. The amount of the azo compound consumed was calculated from the decrease in the optical density after the completion of the reaction (which is indicated by the constancy of the optical

TABLE 1
COMPARISON OF RATES OF SILVER(I)-CATALYSED AND UNCATALYSED OXIDATIONS
[S₂O₈²⁻] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ M; [H⁺] = 1.0 M [HoAc] = 1.6% V/V; Temp. = 30 ± 0.1°
μ = 3.02

Substrate	[Substrate] × 10 ⁶ M	k ₀ × 10 ⁷ moles. lit ⁻¹ . min ⁻¹ of the catalysed reaction in the presence of [Ag ⁺] = 8.0 × 10 ⁻⁴ M.	k ₀ × 10 ¹⁰ moles. lit ⁻¹ . min ⁻¹ of the uncatalysed reaction.
[4, 4' Cl - C ₆ H ₄ - N=N - C ₆ H ₄ - N(CH ₃) ₂] [4]-chloro-Benzol-azo- [4']-dimethyl aniline	2.42	2.70	9.23
[4, 4' NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄ - N=N - C ₆ H ₄ - N(CH ₃) ₂] [4]-nitro-Benzol-azo- [4']-dimethyl aniline	2.50	3.35	7.94
[4]-Dimethyl-amido-azo- Benzol-[4]-Sulphonic acid (Methyl Orange)	2.08	8.10	8.82
[4, 4' HSO ₃ - C ₆ H ₄ - N=N - C ₆ H ₄ - N(CH ₃) ₂] [4]-Dimethyl amido-azo- Benzol-[2]-mono carboxylic acid (Methyl Red)	1.24	5.26	5.67
[2, 4 COOH - C ₆ H ₄ - N=N - C ₆ H ₄ - N(CH ₃) ₂]			

density with time). It was found that for all the aromatic azo compounds studied, 1 mole of the azo compound was found to consume 1 mole of peroxydisulphate. Under the experimental conditions employed acetic acid is not oxidised by peroxydisulphate.

Products of the reaction: The stoichiometry indicates the formation of azoxy compound as the product of the oxidation. This was confirmed by comparing this product with the oxidation product obtained by reaction with hydrogen peroxide, which was earlier reported³ to be an azoxy compound. The identity was established by Co T.L.C and superimposable I.R. spectra of these two products. The I.R. spectrum of the product has shown that $-N(CH_3)_2$ group is not affected thereby proving that the site of attack is $-N=N-$ group.

Results

Several kinetic runs were carried out for the oxidation of each of the azo compounds studied, keeping the concentration of peroxydisulphate at least fifty times that of the concentration of azo compound. The plot of optical density versus time for typical azo compound has been shown in Fig. 1. A straight line is obtained only for the latter part of the reaction. The reaction seems to have an induction period. The linear dependence of the optical density on time after the induction period shows that the reaction is zero order with respect to each of the azo compounds (Fig. 1). The pseudo zero order rate constant k_0 was calculated from the slopes of these straight lines. It is also evident from the figure that the induction period decreases with increasing $Ag(I)$ concentration. A similar behaviour was also observed in the oxidation of other azo

Fig. 1. Zero-Order dependence of rate on the concentration of azo compound.

[4, 4'-Cl-C₆H₄-N=N-C₆H₄-N(CH₃)₂]=2.42 × 10⁻³ M
 [H⁺]=1.0 M [S₂O₈²⁻]=2.0 × 10⁻³ M [HoAc]=1.6% V/V
 Temperature=30 ± 0.1° μ=3.01
 ○—○ [Ag(I)]=1.6 × 10⁻³ M △—△ [Ag(I)]=2.4 × 10⁻³ M
 □—□ [Ag(I)]=3.2 × 10⁻³ M ●—● [Ag(I)]=4.0 × 10⁻³ M

compounds. The rates were also determined for different initial concentrations of each of the azo compounds keeping the concentrations of all the other materials constant. The data were presented in Table 2. It is evident from the data that the rate of the reaction is independent of the concentration of the azo compound showing the zero order kinetics with respect to the azo compound.

TABLE 2

ZERO-ORDER DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON THE CONCENTRATION OF AZO COMPOUND
 [S₂O₈²⁻]=3.5 × 10⁻³ M; [H⁺]=1.0 M; [HoAc]=2.4% V/V; Temp.=30 ± 0.1°
 μ=3.02

Substrate	[Substrate] × 10 ³ M	[Ag ⁺] × 10 ³ M	Rate × 10 ⁷ moles. lit ⁻¹ . min ⁻¹
[4]-chloro-	1.82	2.4	5.58
Benzol-azo-	2.42	2.4	5.58
[4']-Dimethyl aniline	3.03	2.4	5.58
[4, 4' Cl - C ₆ H ₄ - N = N - C ₆ H ₄ - N(CH ₃) ₂]			
[4]-nitro-	1.25	1.6	4.56
Benzol-azo-	1.88	1.6	4.56
[4']-Dimethyl aniline	2.50	1.6	4.57
[4, 4' NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄ - N = N - C ₆ H ₄ - N(CH ₃) ₂]			
[4']-Dimethyl-amido-azo-	2.08	0.8	4.80
Benzol-[4]-Sulphonic acid (Methyl Orange)	2.60	0.8	4.80
	3.12	0.8	4.79
[4, 4' HSO ₃ - C ₆ H ₄ - N = N - C ₆ H ₄ - N(CH ₃) ₂]			
[4]-Dimethyl-amido-azo-	0.74	0.8	3.48
Benzol-[2]-mono carboxylic acid (Methyl Red)	1.24	0.8	3.48
	1.73	0.8	3.48
[2,4 COOH - C ₆ H ₄ - N = N - C ₆ H ₄ - N(CH ₃) ₂]			

The value of k_0 was also determined at different peroxydisulphate concentrations, for the oxidation of each of the azo compounds. Plot of k_0 versus $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$ is a straight line passing through the origin. This shows that the reaction is first order with respect to peroxydisulphate in all the cases (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. First Order dependence of rate on the concentration of $S_2O_8^{2-}$

- $[Ag(I)] = 2.4 \times 10^{-3} M$
 $[4, 4'Cl-C_6H_4-N=N-C_6H_4-N(CH_3)_2] = 2.42 \times 10^{-5} M$
 $[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$
- $[Ag(I)] = 1.6 \times 10^{-3} M$
 $[4, 4'NO_2-C_6H_4-N=N-C_6H_4-N(CH_3)_2] = 2.50 \times 10^{-5} M$
 $[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 1.50 \times 10^{-3} M$
- △—△ $[Ag(I)] = 8.0 \times 10^{-4} M$
 $[4, 4'HCO_2-C_6H_4-N=N-C_6H_4-N(CH_3)_2] = 2.08 \times 10^{-5} M$
 $[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 1.60 \times 10^{-3} M$
- $[Ag(I)] = 8.0 \times 10^{-4} M$
 $[2, 4COOH-C_6H_4-N=N-C_6H_4-N(CH_3)_2] = 1.24 \times 10^{-5} M$
 $[H^+] = 1.0 M; [HoAc] = 1.6\% V/V; \mu = 3.01; Temp. = 30 \pm 0.1^\circ$

The value of k_0 was determined at different $Ag(I)$ concentrations. A plot of k_0 versus $[Ag(I)]$ is a straight line passing through the origin, showing that the reaction is first order with respect to $Ag(I)$ (Fig. 3). This also shows that the extent of uncatalysed reaction is negligibly small. In view of all the above facts, the experimental rate law may be expressed as

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{azo compound}] = k [S_2O_8^{2-}] [Ag^+]$$

Effect of Ionic Strength: The reaction was studied at different ionic strengths by varying the concentration of sodium perchlorate. The increase in ionic strength produced a decrease in the rate of the reaction. A plot of $\log k_0$ versus $\sqrt{\mu}$ is a straight line with a negative slope.

Fig. 3. First Order dependence of rate on the concentration of $Ag(I)$

- $[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$
 $[4, 4'Cl-C_6H_4-N=N-C_6H_4-N(CH_3)_2] = 2.42 \times 10^{-5} M$
 $[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$
 $[4, 4'NO_2-C_6H_4-N=N-C_6H_4-N(CH_3)_2] = 2.50 \times 10^{-5} M$
 $[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 1.50 \times 10^{-3} M$
 $[4, 4'HCO_2-C_6H_4-N=N-C_6H_4-N(CH_3)_2] = 2.08 \times 10^{-5} M$
 $[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 1.60 \times 10^{-3} M$
 $[2, 4COOH-C_6H_4-N=N-C_6H_4-N(CH_3)_2] = 1.24 \times 10^{-5} M$
 $[H^+] = 1.0 M; [HoAc] = 1.6\% V/V; \mu = 3.01; Temp. = 30 \pm 0.1^\circ$

Effect of Acrylonitrile: The reaction mixture with acrylonitrile yielded a white precipitate showing that the reaction initiates vinyl polymerization. Further, the rate measurements before the solid polymer formation have shown that an increase in acrylonitrile concentration reduced the rate of oxidation of azo compounds (Table 3). This is due to the well known effect of acrylonitrile as a scavenger of free radicals, resulting in the inhibition. Thus free radicals seem to be involved in the reaction.

Mechanism :

The observed rate-law $-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{azo compound}] = k[S_2O_8^{2-}][Ag^+]$ suggests that the rate determining step involves Ag^+ and $S_2O_8^{2-}$. This coupled with the observed induction period for the reaction as well as the evidence obtained for free radical formation is suggestive of a chain mechanism.

The application of steady state approximation to $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$, X and Ag^{2+} leads to the rate law

$$\frac{-d}{dt} [\text{azo compound}] = [\text{Ag}^+][\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] \left\{ k_1 + \frac{k_1 k_3 k_4}{k_5} \right\}^{1/2}$$

which is in agreement with the experimental rate law. It is interesting to note that a similar kinetic pattern were reported in Ag(I)-catalysed peroxydisulphate oxidation of methanol⁴, ethanol⁴, glycol⁵, lactic acid⁶, glycerol⁷, propionaldehyde⁸ and urea⁹. In all these cases the first order kinetics was observed with respect to peroxydisulphate and silver(I) and zero order kinetics with respect to the reductant. A similar chain mechanism has been proposed to account for the observed results.

TABLE 3

INFLUENCE OF ACRYLONITRILE CONCENTRATION ON RATE

Substrate	[Substrate] × 10 ⁴ M	[Acrylonitrile] M	k _o × 10 ³ moles.lit ⁻¹ .min ⁻¹
[4]-chloro-Benzol-azo-[4']-Dimethyl aniline	2.42	0.30	1.22
[4, 4' Cl - C ₆ H ₄ - N = N - C ₆ H ₄ - N(CH ₃) ₂]	2.42	0.60	1.10
[4]-nitro-Benzol-azo-[4']-Dimethyl aniline	2.42	0.90	0.87
[4, 4' NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄ - N = N - C ₆ H ₄ - N(CH ₃) ₂]	2.42	1.21	0.64
[4]-nitro-Benzol-azo-[4']-Dimethyl aniline	2.50	0.30	2.64
[4, 4' NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄ - N = N - C ₆ H ₄ - N(CH ₃) ₂]	2.50	0.60	1.89
[4]-nitro-Benzol-azo-[4']-Dimethyl aniline	2.50	0.90	1.23
[4, 4' NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄ - N = N - C ₆ H ₄ - N(CH ₃) ₂]	2.50	1.21	0.87
[4]-Dimethyl-amido-azo-Benzol-[4]-Sulphonic acid (Methyl Orange)	2.08	0.30	5.05
[4, 4' HSO ₃ - C ₆ H ₄ - N = N - C ₆ H ₄ - N(CH ₃) ₂]	2.08	0.60	4.57
[4]-Dimethyl-amido-azo-Benzol-[4]-Sulphonic acid (Methyl Orange)	2.08	0.90	2.93
[4, 4' HSO ₃ - C ₆ H ₄ - N = N - C ₆ H ₄ - N(CH ₃) ₂]	2.08	1.21	2.18
[4]-Dimethyl-amido-azo-Benzol-[2]-mono carboxylic acid (Methyl Red)	1.24	0.30	3.58
[2, 4 COOH - C ₆ H ₄ - N = N - C ₆ H ₄ - N(CH ₃) ₂]	1.24	0.60	2.93
[4]-Dimethyl-amido-azo-Benzol-[2]-mono carboxylic acid (Methyl Red)	1.24	0.90	2.17
[2, 4 COOH - C ₆ H ₄ - N = N - C ₆ H ₄ - N(CH ₃) ₂]	1.24	1.21	2.15

TABLE 4

ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

Temp. = 30 ± 0.1°

Substrate	E K cal.mole ⁻¹	ΔS [‡] cal.deg ⁻¹ .mole ⁻¹
[4]-chloro-Benzol-azo-[4']-Dimethyl aniline	11.8	-48.8
[4, 4' Cl - C ₆ H ₄ - N = N - C ₆ H ₄ - N(CH ₃) ₂]	13.8	-40.9
[4]-nitro-Benzol-azo-[4']-Dimethyl aniline	5.2	-69.9
[4, 4' NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄ - N = N - C ₆ H ₄ - N(CH ₃) ₂]	9.6	-54.7
[4]-Dimethyl-amido-azo-Benzol-[4]-Sulphonic acid (Methyl Orange)		
[4, 4' HSO ₃ - C ₆ H ₄ - N = N - C ₆ H ₄ - N(CH ₃) ₂]		
[4]-Dimethyl-amido-azo-Benzol-[2]-mono carboxylic acid (Methyl Red)		
[2, 4 COOH - C ₆ H ₄ - N = N - C ₆ H ₄ - N(CH ₃) ₂]		

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